

Women Leaders and their Leadership Styles

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14705159

Abstract

Gender inequality is a reality across the globe as women often experience marginalization of all kinds. It is in this regard that Sustainable Development Goal #5 speaks to the promotion of gender equality and empowerment of women, which is regarded as a human rights issue (United Nations, 2015). Although South Africa has made significant strides in addressing gender inequality, especially in government departments and political parties, women remain under-represented in other sectors. For example, 68% of senior leadership positions in public and private sectors are controlled by men. Worldwide, several programmes have been initiated in an attempt to address gender gaps in education, health and political representation. Hence, this article undergoes a study on the facets of women leaders and their styles in emanating their leadership.

Keywords: Women Leadership, Women Empowerment, Leadership Styles.

1. Introduction

Gender inequality is a reality across the globe as women are often marginalised, discriminated against and prevented from advancing. It is in this regard that Sustainable Development Goal #5 speaks to the promotion of gender equality and empowerment of women which is regarded as a human rights issue (United Nations, 2015). Although South Africa has made significant strides in addressing gender inequality, especially in government departments and political parties, women remain under-represented in other sectors. For example, 68% of senior leadership positions in public and private sectors are controlled by men. Worldwide, several programmes have been initiated in an attempt to address gender gaps in education, health and political representation. The 17 sustainable development goals are an attempt to ensure gender equality and empowerment in recognition of the important role women play in societies (United Nations, 2015). It is comforting to learn that more women are now in positions of leadership than before (Keohane, 2020). Although there is some progress in the 21st century as more women are accessing education and many are appointed to managerial positions in the government and private sector (Deshpande, LoBue, Pieter & Sen, 2021), they remain unequal to men as they have limited access to power and resources (Safdar et al, 2021). This paper seeks to highlight the leadership styles of women in leadership. In doing so, it explores the following:

- a. **The role of empowerment and character traits in leadership styles**
- b. **Women and appreciative leadership style**
- c. **Social influence on women's leadership style**

d. Style of leadership implemented to uplift other females

e. Community engagement and leadership style

2. Empowerment, character traits, and Women leadership styles

According to Northouse (2012), leadership is a behavioural process in which one individual inspires a group of individuals (by exhibiting acceptable behaviours) to attain a common goal. Mashele and Alagidede (2021) define leadership as a process of influencing others towards the achievement of a common goal. This suggests that both men and women can provide leadership although, in practice, it is often gender and not competence for and/or experience in leadership roles that determines who is selected for leadership roles (Keohane, 2020). Safdar et al (2021) argue that women empowerment is key to sustainable economic growth, social development and environmental sustainability. This means that women in leadership positions can make a huge impact on the development of our economy as well as social and environmental development. Therefore, ensuring that women are involved in decision-making and that their voices are heard could change the dynamics around women's empowerment. There are clear goals on how to substantially develop and promote equality by providing the same opportunities to women and men, including in decision-making in all kinds of activities. A sustainable path of development can be achieved to ensure that both women's and men's interests are taken into account in the allocation of resources (USAID, 2012). It is essential to flag that empowerment is not a linear process but multifaceted, involving beliefs, individual and collective awareness, as well as behaviour informed by cultural contexts (Huis et al, 2017). They argue that for empowerment to be sustained, it should take place at three social levels, namely, the individual (micro) level, the community (meso) level, and the society (macro) level (Huis et al, 2017). When empowerment takes place in all three dimensions, it strengthens our understanding of what women's empowerment entails and promotes gender equality. We acknowledge that women are not a homogenous group; neither are those in leadership positions. As such, we acknowledge that their personalities and life experiences influence their identities as women and leaders which, in turn, influence their leadership styles. This view is supported by Gakuya and Gichure (2018) who argue that leaders' beliefs and values determine their responses to organisational issues. They add that leadership competencies like wisdom, adaptability, and being able to learn are critical (Gakuya & Gichure, 2018). Women tend to have a more positive approach to leading others and according to a study by Mashele and Alagidede (2021, p. 500) this style of leadership is not surprising since they found that women tend to be "more participative, empathetic, caring and empowering" in their style of leadership. This approachability and consultative leadership style, they add, corroborates other studies which found that women leaders tend to be transformational rather than transactional. Their study also showed women leaders tend to lean on the empathetic side, being concerned about understanding "the situation and context of the issue at hand" (Mashele & Alagidede, 2021, p. 501). Minning (2022) in a study on leadership qualities found that women focus on individual character traits which are linked to the personality of individuals, whilst leadership qualities on the other hand are viewed as a combination of individual character traits that result in particular leadership styles and refers to the way someone may use their respective traits.

3. Women and Appreciative leadership style

According to Whitney, Trosten-Bloom and Radar appreciative leadership is described as,

...a set of practices that turn human potential into positive performance. It is a positive, strength-based approach to human performance, collaboration, and change management. It represents a shift from individualistic and deficit-based leadership processes to relational and dialogical leadership processes. It puts forth a fully affirmative way of working and leading based on the ideas that positive processes get positive results. In essence, appreciative leadership draws on positive power to discover, learn from, and build on the best in people and situations and to make a positive difference in the world. (2010, p. 5)

Whitney and Trosten-Bloom (2011) discuss in detail five strategies of appreciative leadership which contribute to important aspects of continued developmental practice. Each strategy is meant to encourage positivity and release individual ability which ultimately works towards the benefit of the organisation. Each female leader who can focus on appreciative inquiry will then bring the necessary leadership style to grow the organisation in the right direction.

Table 1: Five Strategies of Appreciative Leadership

STRATEGY	DESCRIPTION
1. The wisdom of inquiry	Asking positively powerful questions. Appreciative questions are a ready source of positive power. All you have to do is ask and a wealth of information, ideas and knowledge unfolds. Positive questions are keys to treasure troves of best practices, success stories and creativity. They unlock positive emotions essential to high performance such as acceptance, validation, job satisfaction, confidence and courage. Positive questions are Appreciative Leadership's most powerful tools. They are compelling vehicles for empowerment, fostering risk-taking and guiding value-based performance. They are the means to all learning, change and innovation.
2. The art of illumination	Bringing out the best of people and situations. People's strengths, capabilities, hopes and dreams are a readily abundant yet frequently overlooked source of positive power. Unrecognised and very often underutilised, strengths are a deep well of potential waiting to be tapped. Appreciative Leadership puts strengths to work, transforming them from raw potential into positive results through the art of illumination.
3. The genius of inclusion	Engaging with others to co-create the future. Inclusion – consciously inviting people to engage in co-authoring their future – is a foundational strategy for Appreciative Leadership, and an indispensable practice for unleashing the positive power of today's multicultural, multigenerational and multitalented workforce. Realities are crafted in relationships, through conversations and collaborations. For decisions and plans for the future to satisfy and serve diverse groups of people, all the people whose future it is must be invited into relationships and included in dialogue and decision-making.
4. The courage of inspiration	Awakening the creative spirit. Appreciative Leadership unleashes otherwise latent potential – great ideas, strengths, capabilities and skills – by inspiring creativity, confidence and hope for the future. Even when all the necessary resources are available, nothing changes and nothing of merit happens without inspiration. Inspiration opens people to the source of life that moves through and among us all. It gives people hope and

	courage to shed habitual ways of living and working and move in new, innovative and more life-affirming directions. Inspiration, hope and creativity – three essential ingredients for personal and collective transformation – go hand in hand.
5. The path of integrity	Making choices for the good of the whole. Appreciative Leadership begins and ends with integrity. When you are on the path of integrity, people know it. They follow your ideas and ideals. They model their ways of working after yours. And they contribute their best to the ideals you put forth.

(Whitney & Trosten-Bloom, 2011, pp. 42-43)

4. Styles of leadership implemented to uplift and Mentor aspiring young females

Appreciative Inquiry offers a creative, exploratory and compassionate method to improve positive change through mentoring (Dewar et al, 2020). The collaborative character of appreciative inquiry enables individuals to generate new opportunities, and this collaboration is a crucial component of mentoring (Daskavich et al., 2015; Law and Chan, 2015; Lafrance, 2018). Mentoring has been recognised as a valuable development approach and an affirmative action instrument that can be utilised to support and promote previously disadvantaged women and groups (Mcilongo & Strydom, 2021). This suggests that mentoring young females is a vital tool that could inspire, develop, and empower formerly disadvantaged women in the workforce. Having a productive, positive, affirming female workforce will drive the organisation in a positive direction.

Mentors with advanced experience and knowledge who are committed to fostering the growth of their protégés or mentees can make a big impact on women who aim to become future leaders in organisations (Green-Powell, 2012). This is supported by Smith (2016) who emphasises that mentoring is essential for the professional advancement and success of black African women. As women confront more obstacles than men in the job market, studies indicate that women require mentoring more than men (Abalkhail & Allan, 2015; Hills, 2015). Due to the obstacles experienced strong, positive female mentors are needed to lead teams of strong, positive females since a role model and a sense of identification are crucial.

Transformational leadership has been perceived by many as a leadership style that most women mentors apply to motivate protégés to bring about positive changes (Cherry, 2022). Transformational leaders are typically dynamic, enthusiastic, and driven. Not only are these leaders concerned and invested in the process, but they are also committed to the success of every member of the group (Begum, Begum, Rustam & Rustam, 2017). Transformational leaders can motivate people to shift their expectations, perceptions, and motives to work towards a common objective under their vision and personality.

Palmer and Jones (2019) conducted a study on the experiences and views of mentoring connections among women academics, as well as the extent to which these relationships aided in the pursuit and accomplishment of tenure. Their findings show that through experiences with women mentors, participants thought that mentoring connections between women can help women professors overcome the issues they face in their personal and professional positions. In addition, they believed that creating opportunities for women to form naturally occurring mentoring connections can assist tenure-track women professors in navigating the tenure process more efficiently. Successful mentoring relationships require selecting mentors with traits such as perceiving the mentoring relationship as part of a larger system - the academy who are honest, attentive, and willing to offer advice to mentees. In

addition, participants believed that woman-to-woman mentoring is more successful when holistic and communal, and less successful when mentors prioritise their progress over the development of others. Hence, the importance of transformational leadership style in advancing others.

5. Social influence on women's leadership style

Despite the success that women have had in ascending to leadership roles and the influence they exert in societies, they still face obstacles imposed by gender stereotypes (Madsen & Andrade, 2018). This is common in many societies, regardless of women's age, race, education, and experience or management level (Eisend, 2019). This is because societies still view men as agents of change, even though that perception is gradually shifting as women become more involved in community development programmes. Although women remain underrepresented in leadership positions, those who have made it in such positions have made considerable progress in the aspects of community engagement and development. Community engagement may be influenced by the leader's ability to motivate them to work harder and believe in themselves. As more women assume leadership positions, the disparities between their leadership styles and those of men in comparable positions will continue to garner attention (Mashele & Alagidede, 2020). Numerous studies have been conducted to demonstrate initiatives from different sectors to advance women in leadership and to show the strength, innovative and productive skills they possess as successful leaders, but barriers still exist in their societies (Potvin, Burdfield-Steel, Potvin, & Heap, 2018). It is evident that the gender roles imposed by society unconsciously determine women's leadership styles.

Sharif (2019) notes that women in leadership positions are now being perceived to be more influential when engaging with communities despite having the same leadership style as men. This could be due to their personality traits (Nkomo, 2011). From a psychological standpoint, women and men differ in their communication styles and in their attempts to influence others. These gender variations in communication and persuasion strategies determine the leadership style differences between men and women (Merchant, 2012). Women are known to use communication as a tool to strengthen social bonds and build relationships whereas men use communication to establish authority and obtain practical results (Merchant, 2012). While leadership behaviours are mostly influenced by environment, preferences, competencies, and experiences, there are a few factors that also play a role (Guay, 2013). According to Sharif (2019), transformational leadership is often reflected in the behaviours of women in positions of leadership. Transformational leadership, the style of leadership found to be the most prominent style of leadership amongst female leaders (Bornman, 2019), is founded on the concept of subordinate growth. Transformational leaders assess the capacity and potential of each subordinate to do a given task or job while keeping in mind the prospect of expanding subordinates' responsibilities and authority in the future (Eliyana & Wijalanti, 2020). Four components comprise transformative leadership: individualised concern, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and idealised influence (Mashele & Alagidede, 2020). A transformational leader can unite people, and modify their beliefs, attitudes, and personal ambitions to achieve his or her goals, and even exceed them.

Most female leaders work and live in their communities and active participation in district-related activities makes for community leadership. According to Samanta (2021), "community leadership is all about the welfare of the people they represent", solving

problems, and highlighting crucial issues to facilitate the social change that is required. The heart of community leadership is protecting and supporting the 'we' (Hernandez-Swanson, 2021). This is fundamentally an African concept: "umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu" which translates to "I am because you are" and embraces the notion of humanity and should sit at the core of a leader's sense of responsibility. As a community leader, one has a fundamental responsibility to protect the public. According to Hernandez-Swanson (2021), community leaders need to practice inclusion and maintain and respect cultural traditions.

Strong role models are significant personalities in women leader lives and this was supported by relevant research (Galambos & Hughes, 2000) which, for example, recommends that leadership skills may be fostered within the family unit, organised female sports groups, community service organisations and special interest groups. Mentoring is another factor that creates a sense of empowerment, and safety, and helps create a healthy self-concept. Mentors vary and include teachers, neighbours, coaches, and grandparents who inspire, support and motivate young women to actualise their potential by exploring new opportunities available. Hanlon and Taylor (2022) highlight that although there are increasing numbers of females in leadership positions in sports organisations, females are still under-represented and gender inequality is a reality. Citing Elling et al. (2018) Hanlon and Taylor (2022) confirm that there are areas where progress has been made, board representation being one example. However, male privilege, power, and dominance generally, continue in the field of sport leadership.

Gender equality and empowerment of women and girls was one of the 17 sustainable development goals launched in the United Nations 2030 agenda (United Nations, 2016). As a result, the idea of mentoring, developing, and advancing women for leadership roles has been prominent in government and private spheres. Empowerment is defined as the processes by which women can organise themselves to increase their self-reliance, proclaim their autonomous right to make decisions, and manage resources that will help them challenge and eliminate their subservience (Crittenden, Crittenden & Ajjan, 2019). Empowering women in emerging economies would not only increase household welfare but will also have a favourable effect on the social and financial well-being of nations through improved education, poverty reduction, and reduced violence. Multiple studies have demonstrated that sustainable development is impossible without the empowerment and equality of women. Consequently, it is stated that gender equality is a human rights issue, a precondition for sustainable development, and an indication of such growth (Moodly & Toni, 2019).

Poltera (2019) conducted a case study exploring examples of women's leadership in African contexts. The study highlighted how women in leadership positions engage with communities and how they perceive leadership and/or conduct it within a specific setting on the continent. It also showed how race, gender, class, culture, sexuality, and other social characteristics can enable or constrain leadership practice. Tetteh (2022) relies on the key role that women have played throughout African history in shaping the culture of their communities. History reflects the contributions of influential women leaders who have played vital roles in the development of their communities.

Conclusion

Influential women leaders have a key role to play in the development of the communities within which they work, live and play and the impact that women can make in sustainable development is immeasurable. Where they will not only empower themselves but the entire society with which they interact. Therefore, organisations and communities must

continue to focus on strengthening women's leadership skills and capacities through a variety of leadership development programs and interventions which will eventually uplift the societies within which the women work, reside and perform. This appreciative inquiry has a ripple effect with far-reaching consequences.

References

- [1] Abalkhail, J. M. (2019). Women's career development in an Arab Middle Eastern context. *Human Resource Development International*, 22(2), 177-199. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13678868.2018.1499377>
- [2] Safdar, S, Isaac, N., Zia, M., Zakar, R., & Fischer, F. (2021) Determinants of women's empowerment in Pakistan: evidence from Demographic and Health Surveys, 2012–13 and 2017–18. Abbas et al. *BMC Public Health*, 21:1328. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11376-6>
- [3] Abdallah, J., & Jibai, S. (2020). Women in leadership: Gender personality traits and skills. *Business Excellence and Management*, 10(1), 5-15. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/rom/bemann/v10y2020i1p5-15.html>
- [4] Al-Ghazali, B. M. (2020). Transformational leadership, career adaptability, job embeddedness and perceived career success: a serial mediation model. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. DOI/10.1108/LODJ-10-2019-0455/full/html.
- [5] Al-Qahtani, A.M., Ibrahim, H.A., Elgzar, W.T., El Sayed, H.A., Essa, R.M. & Abdelghaffar, T.A. (2021). The Role of Self-Esteem and Self-Efficacy in Women Empowerment in The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: A Cross-Sectional Study. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 25(1), 69-78. DOI: 10.29063/ajrh2021/v25i1s.7
- [6] Alqahtani, T. H. (2020). The status of women in leadership. *Archives of Business Research*, 8 (2) 294-299. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340514638>
- [7] Appreciative Inquiry Australia. "4D-Cycle." Appreciative Inquiry Australia. <https://appreciativeinquiry.com.au/forum-2010/background/invitation/4d-cycle/>
- [8] April, K., & Sikatali, N. (2019). Personal and interpersonal assertiveness of female leaders in skilled technical roles. *Effective Executive*, XXII (4), 33–58. <https://sajhrm.co.za/index.php/sajhrm/rt/printerFriendly/1326/2202>
- [9] Baroudi, S., & David, S. A. (2020). Nurturing female leadership skills through peer mentoring role: A study among undergraduate students in the United Arab Emirates. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 74(4), 458-474. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/hequ.12249>
- [10] Blue, G. D. (2022). *The Impact of Mentoring on the Career Advancement of African American Women to Leadership Management Roles in Business* (Doctoral dissertation, Campbellsville University). <https://cjcd-rcdc.ceric.ca/index.php/cjcd/article/download/263/251>.
- [11] Bornman, D.A.J. (2019). Gender-based leadership perceptions and preferences of Generation Z as future business leaders in South Africa. *Acta Commercii*, 19(1), a708. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ac.v19i1.708>
- [12] Bozer, G., & Jones, R. J. (2018). Understanding the factors that determine workplace coaching effectiveness: A systematic literature review. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 27(3), 342-361. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2018-17621-005>

- [13] Cherry, K. (2022). Transformational Leadership: A Closer Look at the Effects of Transformational Leadership. *Personality Psychology*.
<https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-transformational-leadership-2795313>
- [14] Coetzee, M., & Moosa, M., (2020). Leadership contingencies in the retention of women in higher education. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management/SA Tydskrif vir Menslikehulpbronbestuur*, 18(0), a1326. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v18i0.1326>
- [15] Cooperrider, D.L., Whitney, D., & Stavros, J.M. (2008). *Appreciative Inquiry handbook: For leaders of change*. (2nded.). California: Crown Custom Publishing. <https://www.bkconnection.com/static/Appreciative-Inquiry-EXCERPT.pdf>
- [16] Crittenden, V. L., Crittenden, W. F., & Ajjan, H. (2019). Empowering women micro-entrepreneurs in emerging economies: The role of information communications technology. *Journal of Business Research*, 98, 191-203. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2019-15761-016>
- [17] Dashper, K. (2020). Mentoring for gender equality: Supporting female leaders in the hospitality industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 88, 102397. <https://eprints.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/id/eprint/6221/1/MentoringGenderEqualitySupportingFemaleLeadersHospitalityIndustryAM-DASHPER.pdf>
- [18] Daskavich, T.J., Jardine, D.A., Tseng, J., Correa, R., Stagg, B.C., Jacob, K.M., Harwood, J. L., 2015. Promotion of wellness and mental health awareness among physicians in training: perspective of a national, multispecialty panel of residents and fellows. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 143-147. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-07-01-42>.
- [19] Dewar, B., Stulz, V., Buliak, A., Connolly, L., McLaughlin, K., Newport, K., ... & Drayton, N. (2020). Exploring and developing student midwives' experiences (ESME)—An appreciative inquiry study. *Midwifery*, 91, 102844. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0266613820302163>
- [20] Eisend, M. (2019). Gender roles. *Journal of Advertising*, 48(1), 72-80. DOI/10.1080/00913367.2019.1566103
- [21] Elias, E. (2018) Lessons learned from women in leadership positions: How working women can survive and thrive. *Work* 59 (175-181). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5870009/>
- [22] Faizan, R., Nair, S. L. S., & Haque, A. U. (2018). The effectiveness of feminine and masculine leadership styles in relation to contrasting gender's performances. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 17. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326156554_The_effectiveness_of_feminine_and_masculine_leadership_styles_in_relation_to_contrasting_gender's_performances
- [23] Gakuya M.W. & Gichure, J. (2018). Influence of women leadership on governance of County governments in Kenya: A case study of Nairobi County government. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5 (2) 214-223.
- [24] Galambos, C.M. & Hughes, S.L. (2000). Using Political and Community Activism to Develop Leadership Skills in Women. *Race, Gender & Class*, 7(4), 18-35. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41955724>
- [25] Gender Links. For Equality and Justice. (2021). Theory of Change: Violence Against Women Baseline studies in South Africa, Mauritius, Botswana, Zambia, Zimbabwe and Lesotho. <http://www.genderlinks.org.za/page/gender-justice-measuring-gbv>

- [26] Griggs, D.M. & Crain-Dorough, M. (2021). Appreciative inquiry's potential in Hanlon, C. & Taylor, T. (2022). Women leaders in sport: a community of practice programme to create social learning, *Managing Sport and Leisure*. DOI: 10.1080/23750472.2022.2051727
- [27] Hastings, L. J., & Kane, C. (2018). Distinguishing mentoring, coaching, and advising for leadership development. *New directions for student leadership*, 2018(158), 9-22. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/yd.20284>
- [28] Hernandez-Swanson, J. (2021). Protecting and sustaining the 'we': Three leadership styles in communities of colour. University of Minnesota Extension. <https://extension.umn.edu/community-news-and-insights/protecting-and-sustaining-we-three-leadership-styles-communities-color>
- [29] Hideg, I. & Shen, W. (2019). Why still so few? A theoretical model of the role of benevolent sexism and career support in the continued underrepresentation of women in leadership positions. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 26 (3) 287-303. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1548051819849006>
- [30] Jones, M. S., & Solomon, J. (2019). Challenges and supports for women conservation leaders. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 1(6), e36. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332675588_Challenges_and_supports_for_women_conservation_leaders
- [31] Keohane, N. O. (2020). Women, power & leadership. *Daedalus*, 149(1), 236-250. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/48563044>
- [32] Kiamba, J. M. (2009). Women and leadership positions: Social and cultural barriers to success. Wagadu, Volume 6, *Journal of International Women's Studies*, Volume 10: 1, 89. <http://sites.cortland.edu/wagadu/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2014/02/kiamba.pdf>
- [33] Kim, S., Hong, S., Magnusen, M. J., & Rhee, Y. (2020). Hard knock coaching: A cross-cultural study of the effects of abusive leader behaviors on athlete satisfaction and commitment through interactional justice. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 15(5-6), 597-609. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1747954120933405>
- [34] Lafrance, T., (2018). Exploring the intrinsic benefits of nursing preceptorship: a personal perspective. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 33, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2018.08.018>.
- [35] Law, B.Y., Chan, E.A., 2015. The experience of learning to speak up: a narrative inquiry on newly graduated registered nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing* 24, 1837–1848. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.12805>.
- [36] Madsen, S. R., & Andrade, M. S. (2018). Unconscious gender bias: Implications for women's leadership development. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 12(1), 62-67. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jls.21566>
- [37] Manzi, F., & Heilman, M. E. (2021). Breaking the glass ceiling: For one and all? *Journal of Personality and social psychology*, 120(2), 257. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2020-87902-001>
- [38] Mashele, W. & Alagidede I.P. (2021). The appropriate leadership styles in times of crisis: a study of women in senior leadership positions in South Africa. *Gender in Management: International Journal*, Vol 77 (4) 494-508. https://www.gestaldt.com/uploads/1/1/7/2/117239124/gestaldt_women_in_leadership.pdf

- [39] Mcilongo, M., & Strydom, K. (2021). The significance of mentorship in supporting the career advancement of women in the public sector. *Heliyon*, 7(6), e07321. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844021014249>
- [40] Minning, L. (2022). 10 Types of Leadership: Are You the Right Type of Leader. *ActiveCampaign*. <https://www.activecampaign.com/blog/types-of-leadership>
- [41] Moodly, A., & Toni, N. (2019, April). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors in Empowerment of Women Towards Leadership: A Study in Higher Education (South Africa). In *ICGR 2019 2nd International Conference on Gender Research* (p. 407). Academic Conferences and Publishing Limited. <https://www.journals.ac.za/index.php/sajhe/article/view/917>
- [42] Moore, M.L., Cangemi, J.P. & Ingram, J.I. (2013). Appreciative Leadership and Opportunity – Centric Approaches to Organization Success. *Organization Development Journal*, 48-53. <https://positivepsychology.com/appreciative-inquiry/>
- [43] Morgan, N., & Pritchard, A. (2019). Gender Matters in Hospitality (invited paper for 'luminaries' special issue of *International Journal of Hospitality Management*). *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76, 38-44. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0278431918305061>
- [44] Oregon State University. (2022). Our approach to community engagement and leadership. <https://cel.oregonstate.edu/about/our-approach>
- [45] Palmer, E. M., & Jones, S. J. (2019). Woman–woman mentoring relationships and their roles in tenure attainment. *Journal of women and gender in higher education*, 12(1), 1-17. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/19407882.2019.1568264>
- [46] Passmore, H. A., Yang, Y., & Sabine, S. (2022). An extended replication study of the well-being intervention, the noticing nature intervention (NNI). *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 1-21. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.840273/full>
- [47] Phakeng, M. (2015). Leadership: The invisibility of African women and the masculinity of power. *South African Journal of Science*, 111(11/12). <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2015/a0126>. <https://sajs.co.za/article/view/3835>
- [48] Poltera, J. (2019). Exploring examples of women's leadership in African contexts. *Agenda*, 33(1), 3-8. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10130950.2019.1602977>
- [49] Pooja, & Kumar, P. (2021). A comparative study of the leadership skills of the millennial male and millennial female managerial leaders in the Indian service sector. *International Journal of Services, Economics and Management*, 12(1), 41-59. <https://econpapers.repec.org/RePEc:ids:injsem:v:12:y:2021:i:1:p:41-59>
- [50] Potvin, D. A., Burdfield-Steel, E., Potvin, J. M., & Heap, S. M. (2018). Diversity begets diversity: A global perspective on gender equality in scientific society leadership. *PLoS one*, 13(5), e0197280. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0197280>
- [51] Pranathi, B.K.P. & Lathabhavan, R. (2021). A study on role of woman in leadership positions. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Applied Sciences and Engineering*, 4(12), 940-943. DOI:10.29027/IJIRASE.v4. i12.2021.program evaluation and research. *Qualitative Research Journal*. 21(4), 375-393. https://www.ijirase.com/assets/paper/issue_12/volume_4/Vol-4-Issue-12-940-943.pdf

- [52] Railey, M. (2020). *A Phenomenological Study of Black Women with Depression, Holding Senior Leadership Positions* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Phoenix). <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED578085>
- [53] Samanta, S. (2021). 10 Qualities For Community Leaders. *Open Growth. Leadership for All*. <https://www.opengrowth.com/article/10-qualities-for-community-leaders>
- [54] Sharif, K. (2019). Transformational leadership behaviours of women in a socially dynamic environment. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331962415_Transformational_leadership_behaviours_of_women_in_a_socially_dynamic_environment
- [55] Shepered, S. (2017). Why are there so few female leaders in higher education: A case of structure and agency. *Management in Education*, 31(2), 82–87. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0892020617696631>
- [56] Southern African Development Community. (2008). Protocol on Gender and Development. https://www.sadc.int/files/8713/5292/8364/Protocol_on_Gender_and_Development_2008.pdf
- [57] Tetteh, H.S. (2022). The Contribution of Women in Leadership in Africa and How the UN is Partnering with the AU to Help Prepare the Next Generation of Women Leaders in Africa. *Women peace and Security*. <https://www.accord.org.za/conflict-resilience/conflict-resilience-monitor-10-march-2022/>
- [58] Toh, T., & Ruot, K. (2019). The role of traits in the leadership process. Available at SSRN 3441179. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335308452_The_Role_of_Traits_in_the_Leadership_Process
- [59] United Nations (2016), “The Sustainable Development Goals Report”, United Nations, New York, NY. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/publications/sustainable-development-goals-report-2016.html>
- [60] Van Ginkel, G., Van Drie, J., & Verloop, N. (2018). Mentor teachers' views of their mentees. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 26(2), 122-147. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13611267.2018.1472542>
- [61] Whitney, D. & Trosten-Bloom, A. (2013). Five Strategies of Appreciative Leadership. *AI Practitioner*, 13(1), 41-43. <https://positivechange.org/five-strategies-of-appreciative-leadership/>
- [62] Whitney, D., Trosten-Bloom, A. & Rader, K. (2010). Leading Positive Performance: A Conversation About Appreciative Leadership. *Performance Improvement*, 49(3), 5-10. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227718266_Leading_positive_performance_A_conversation_about_appreciative_leadership
- [63] Wielenga, C. (2022). Introduction: Women's Roles in Justices Practices in Southern Africa. In *African Feminisms and Women in the Context of Justice in Southern Africa* (pp. 1-18). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337031575>
- [64] Zaman, U., Nawaz, S., Tariq, S., & Humayoun, A. A. (2019). Linking transformational leadership and “multi-dimensions” of project success: Moderating effects of project flexibility and project visibility using PLS-SEM. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*.

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
மதிப்பாய்வு செய்யப்படும் இதழ்

Volume 4, Issue 2, November 2024

E-ISSN – 2583-715X

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354401965_Transformational_Leadership_and_Project_Success_Serial_Mediation_of_Team-Building_and

Author Contribution Statement: NIL

Author Acknowledgement: Nil

Author Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

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